

Studies in Heterocyclics : XI. Mass Spectral Study of Benzo-Thiazolo-Triazepines

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The mass spectral study of 3-phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine-10-thiol, 5-methyl-3-phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine-10-thiol and 3-phenyl 9H, 10H benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine is being reported.

IN continuation of our study in heterocyclics herewith we wish to report the mass spectral fragmentation pattern of three members of benzo-thiazolo-triazepines. The synthesis of these derivatives i.e. 3-phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepines-10-thiol (I), 5-methyl-3-phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepines-10-thiol (II), and 3-phenyl 9H, 10H benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine (III) has been reported earlier². The thiazole part gives a set of characteristic fragments³ such as cleavages along (a) and (b) i.e. m/e 134 (9%), 45 (9%) for I; m/e 134 (73%), 45 (83%) for II and m/e 134 (53%), 45 (58%) for III.

Chart 1

Chart 1 (Contd.)

3-Phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine-10-thiol (Chart 1; Table 1): The successive losses of CS and S from I provide azetidino-benzo-triazinium ion (V; m/e 233; 32%) is similar to the losses of CS, CS₂, and S from benzothiazole-2-thiol⁴. The other prominent mode of fragmentation is loss of NCS through α-cleavage.

5-Methyl-3-phenyl-benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine-10-thiol (II; Table 1): In addition to the parallel mode as described for I, II also undergoes a rearrangement after the loss of CH₃. The rearranged product m/e 249 (69%) further fragmentates giving

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TABLE I—MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS* I AND II

Sl. No.	Compound I		Compound II	
	Ion peaks	Relative abundance %	Ion peaks	Relative abundance %
1.	309	40	325	7
2.	265	7	324	19
3.	252	5	<u>323</u>	<u>100</u>
4.	251	18	308	28
5.	<u>250</u>	<u>100</u>	265	76
6.	233	32	264	78
7.	152	40	249	69
8.	134	9	248	70
9.	126	10	222	53
10.	121	5	134	73
11.	116	6	105	91
12.	104	5	104	85
13.	103	8	92	60
14.	102	14	91	72
15.	91	8	90	91
16.	90	14	89	73
17.	89	12	78	70
18.	77	19	77	70
19.	76	8	65	78
20.	65	7	51	77
21.	64	6	50	69
22.	59	10	45	83
23.	52	5	39	67
24.	51	10		
25.	45	9		
26.	39	20		

* Peak underlined show the base peak.

rise to ion peaks m/e 248 (70%) and 222 (53%) by the loss of H and HCN.

3-phenyl 9H, 10H benzo [f] thiazolo [3,2-a] [1,3,5] triazepine (III; Chart 2; Table 2): The molecular ion peak m/e 279 (94%) is accompanied by m/e 278 (83%) and m/e 277 (86%) which arise from the successive losses of hydrogen atoms. Also the sequential losses of CH_2 and H from the parent ion gave rise to thiazolo-benzo-triazinium ion (XVII) m/e 264 (19%). The loss of CH_2 from the parent ion (m/e 279; 94%) is

supported by the appearance of corresponding metastable peak. The rational set of ions as m/e 251 (M-28; 97%), m/e 250 (M-29; 100%), m/e 234 (M-45; 82%) and m/e 145 (M-134; 22%) through the losses of CH_2N , CH_2NH , $\text{HC}\equiv\text{S}^+$ and $\text{H}_5\text{C}_6-\text{C}=\text{CH}$ respectively. The

Chart 2 (Contd.)

Table 2 (Cont.)

TABLE 2—MASS SPECTRAL DATA OF COMPOUND III

Sl. No.	Ion peaks	Relative abundance %
1.	281	0.4
2.	280	17
3.	279	94
4.	278	83
5.	277	86
6.	265	78
7.	264	19
8.	251	97
9.	<u>250</u>	<u>100</u>
10.	249	94
11.	234	82

12.	233	75
13.	224	70
14.	223	73
15.	207	64
16.	206	65
17.	205	58
18.	181	47
19.	180	50
20.	179	45
21.	165	29
22.	152	24
23.	149	61
24.	148	64
25.	145	22
26.	134	53
27.	121	42
28.	116	83
29.	108	19
30.	104	50
31.	103	53
32.	102	54
33.	91	39
34.	90	36
35.	89	41
36.	77	46
37.	76	43
38.	64	39
39.	51	67
40.	50	66
41.	45	58
42.	39	39
43.	32	50

* Ion peak underlined indicates the base peak.

extrusion of HCN from thiazolo-benzimidazolium ion (XVIII; m/e 251; 97%) undergoes further fragmentation to m/e 224 (70%), 223 (73%), 121 (42%), 116 (83%), 108 (19%), and 103 (53%) successively. The mass ion 152 may be the product of rearrangement from m/e 250 (100%).

Experimental

3-Phenyl-benzo [*f*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3,5] triazepine-10-thiol, 5-methyl-3-phenyl benzo [*f*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3-5] triazepine-10-thiol and 3-phenyl-9*H*, 10*H* benzo [*f*] thiazolo [3,2-*a*] [1,3,5] triazepine were prepared by the method reported already by us⁽²⁾.

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